

CRUISE – REPORT

2024_TA_06

DEEP-TRACE

18th to 30th of September 2024

Technical report no. 134, 2024

Pinngortitaleriffik, Greenland Institute of Natural Resources

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By

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III

Summary

The Deep-Trace cruise was carried out between the 18th and 30th of September 2024 on board RV Tarajoq. The purpose of the cruise was to better understand environmental conditions and species dynamics in East Greenland, Tasiilaq region along a gradient from coastal shelf along glacially derived trenches towards the continental shelf edge and shelf slope. Geomorphology, benthic biodiversity and community composition, oceanography, sediment chemistry and composition were assessed along three trenches in this region.

Eqikkaaneq

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Abstrakt

Det videnskabelige togt Deep-Trace blev gennemført i perioden 18. og 30. september 2024 om bord på forskningsskibet RV Tarajoq. Formålet med togtet var at få en bedre forståelse af miljøforhold og artsdynamik i Tasiilaq-regionen i Østgrønland. Togtets rute fulgte kontinentalsklens kant samt transekter herfra og mod kysten henover undersøiske kanaler udgravet af historiske gletsjere. Under togtet undersøgte forskerne havbundens morfologi og sedimenters sammensætning og kemiske forhold, der er grundlag for dyrelivet på havbunden. Ud fra undervandsvideoer og prøver fra havbunden registrerede forskerne det benthiske dyreliv og biodiversiteten og sammensætning af arter.

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank the crew of the RV Tarajoq for their invaluable assistance and support during our time on board. The success of the Deep Trace cruise is a testament to the enthusiasm, dedication, and exceptional teamwork we experienced throughout this survey.

The Deep Trace cruise was funded by the Government of Greenland partnership agreement with the European Commission (Green Growth Programme)

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Scientific motivation

Very little is known about the seafloor in Greenland. Commitments by the Government of Greenland to protect 30% of its seas by 2030 and growing pressure to take the impact of demersal fishing on seafloor ecosystems into account for MSC certifications has sparked an increased interest in better mapping and understanding benthic ecosystems around Greenland. Although a benthic bycatch monitoring programme has been implemented by the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources since 2016, information gained here is focused on large epifauna captured in commercial trawls within fisheries zones and often lacks contextual information, such as seafloor morphology, substrata composition, hydrodynamic conditions, nutrient and primary production availability. These parameters are often driving the distribution of benthic species and are instrumental in creating reliable habitat maps.

In 2024, the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources received support from the European Union Green Growth fund for a 4 year project (Greenland Seabed Ecosystem Survey) with the goal to improve the ongoing monitoring work, survey understudied areas and provide a better understanding of the Greenlandic seafloor ecosystem. This project is meant to aid pinpointing biodiversity hotspots, areas vulnerable to anthropogenic impact (Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem Indicator Taxa) as well as identify unique and rare ecosystems and provide a better understanding of species distribution across Greenland. Additionally, this project is attempting to consider fairly novel parameters in Marine Spatial Planning, such as potential blue carbon habitats across the Greenland EEZ.

The Deep-Trace cruise (18th to 30th of September 2024) on the GINR ship RV Tarajoq was the first scientific cruise carried out as part of the GSES project. The primary aim of this cruise was to trace changes in biodiversity and species composition from the coast along the shelf and into the deep sea of the continental slope, integrating common geomorphological features along the Greenland seafloor such as glacially derived deep trenches on the shelf. The secondary aim was to collect contextual information to help understand shifts in species composition and the tertiary aim was to trace carbon transport from the coast into the deep sea and highlight areas with greater carbon content along the East Greenland Shelf.

The large bay in front of Tasiilaq is known to be a biological hotspot with high abundances of different whale species and a comparatively large occurrence of corals found here. Thus, this area was the primary focus on this cruise, with another hotspot for Greenland halibut being surveyed further South. Samples were collected for 4 work packages on each station

1. Geomorphology: Multibeam data was collected continuously throughout the survey area
2. Benthic Ecosystems: video and imagery was collected at all stations, these were followed up with standardised beamtrawl surveys at the coast, the middle of the trough, on the shelf and on the bottom of the continental shelf, in order to ID all species to lowest possible taxonomic resolution and capture small taxa that are not identifiable from video data.

3. Oceanographic data: CTD profiles were collected from all realised stations. Water samples were taken throughout the water column and assessed for nutrient and chlorophyll content.
4. Sediment biogeochemistry: Sediment cores were taken where possible using a multicorer. Cores were assessed for oxygen penetration, microbial respiration, chlorophyll content and porosity. Samples were taken for eDNA analysis of macroalgal carbon sources, inorganic and organic carbon content. When possible, sediment cores were sampled for infauna.

1.2 Scientific and Ship Personal

1.2.1 Scientists

Nadescha Zwerschke	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Greenland, (PSO)
Alenya Merz	Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, Netherlands
Christian Sølbeck	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Greenland
David Barnes	British Antarctic Survey, UK
Diana Krawczyk	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Greenland
Duncan Sinclair	British Antarctic Survey, UK
Fletcher Thompsen	Technical University of Denmark, Denmark
Helle Siegstad	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Greenland
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Katharina Lysgård Hammer	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Greenland
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Narissa Bax	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Greenland
Pia Scaramiglia	University of the Westfjords, Iceland
Ryan Mathews	British Antarctic Survey, UK
Tobias Vonnahme	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Greenland

1.2.2 Ship personal

Officer

Jákup G. Mikkelsen	Master
Martin Grund	1 st Officer
Erlendur Simonsen	1 st Officer

Engineer

Tórður Nielsen	Chief Engineer
Ári Hansen	
Helgi Samson	

Deck crew

Magnus Petersen

Johan Egede

Hansseraq Markussen

Boas Augustussen

Mona Olsen

Apollo Rosing-Larsen

Interior crew

Andreas Mikaelson

Cook

Karoline Johansen-Dalager

Service

1.3 Cruise Diary

Date	Event
18th of September 2024	Leaving Reykjavik at 9.30, mobilisation and setting up of multicorer, steaming to station OT1_9
19th of September 2024	Steaming, mobilisation, setting up of video sled, arrival at Station OT1_8 at 22.00. Station OT1_8 was chosen as first site to test deployment of multicorer as it was more shallow than site OT1_9. Hard bottom at OT1_8 but multicorer seemed to work well
20th of September 2024	Work continues on OT1, Multicore on OT1_7 and OT1_8 were aborted because of hard bottom. OT1_4 was not successful because of currents, OT1_3 was abandoned because of weather. Water samples, CTD and Video recording collected from OT1_6, OT1_5 and OT1_4, Beamtrawl collected from station OT1_7 and OT1_4
21st of September 2024	Work continues on OT1, Multicore on OT1_2 successful, issues on OT1_1 owing to hard bottom, only 3 cores collected. MC attempted on OT1_4 and OT1_5 but came up empty despite INAMAR showing soft sediment. MC trouble shooting was carried out throughout the night. Water, CTD and Video recordings were collected from OT1_1, OT1_2, OT1_3, OT1_4. Video from station OT1_3 was lost. However, video imagery from 2020 for the same station is available.
22nd of September 2024	Work continues on OT1, Multicore was attempted on OT1_9 but was unsuccessful. The slope was hard substratum owing to strong currents. Water, CTD and Video recordings were collected for Station OT1_7, OT1_8, OT1_9. Video from station OT1_8 was lost. Deployment of sledge took too long for deployment causing the camera to run out of battery before reaching bottom on station OT1_9. Still images were taken. Beamtrawl was collected from OT1_9. New data transfer protocol for videos and imagery were put in place to prevent further loss of video data

23rd of September 2024	Sailing to OT2, Multicore release pins were made longer to prevent firing on water entry. Successful deployment of MC at OT2_6, OT2_5. No MC at OT2_7 owing to hard bottom. Water and video were collected for OT2_8. Beamtrawl was collected at OT2_7
24th of September 2024	Work continues on OT2, Multicore was collected at OT2_4 (3 cores), Hard bottom on OT2_1, OT2_2, OT2_3 despite being in 1000 m depth trench. Water, CTD and Video were collected for OT2_4, OT2_3, OT2_2 and OT2_1. Video from OT2_4 was not useable as Laserblock was loose on video sled. Beamtrawl was collected at station OT2_1 and OT2_4. OT2_1 had many crinoids
25th of September 2024	Work continues on OT2, Multicore was unsuccessful at OT2_3 owing to hard bottom, Station OT2_8 was placed ~ 10nm further south for MC, as video confirmed no mud at the original station - successful deployment. Water, CTD and Video collected at OT2_4, OT2_5, OT2_6, OT2_7. Video was also collected at OT2_3. The laser alignment on the laser block had changed, A temporary fix was installed. Clamp of laser block was modified for better grip. CTD was lowered on the extendable winch for the first time. Winch malfunctioned and CTD hit bottom at OT2_7, batteries of CTD were empty so only recorded until 375m at this station. Data for CTD and Rosette was not instantly entered into the database - stations were entered the next day with a later event number. Beamtrawl was collected from OT2_7. Observation of stalked crinoids here.
26th of September 2024	Sailing to OT3. Water, CTD and Video recordings were collected for OT3_6, OT3_5, OT3_4 and OT3_3. Video sled deployment was changed to using guidelines from the side winches which worked very well. Video deployment on OT3_4 was semi successful. Course change throughout deployment, sled remained on the same spot for more than 10 min of deployment. Multicore was attempted at station OT3_3, but was unsuccessful. Beamtrawl had big boulders in it and got ripped on station OT3_3. Crew managed to fix it before the next station

27th of September 2024	Work continues on OT3. Beamtrawl deployed at OT3_1 and OT3_6, Water and Video collected more rapidly. Between Station OT3_2 and OT3_3 a muddy spot was detected by Innomar. MC corer was successfully deployed. Station was recorded as Extra 1 in database. Station 3 was attempted again unsuccessfully, station OT3_4 was collected (~70cm sediment cores), OT3_5 yielded enough sediment for respiration and chlorophyll. Station OT3_6 was unsuccessful.
28th of September 2024	Steaming to Nuuk, Cleaning, Packing, Data checking, Cruise photo
29th of September 2024	Steaming to Nuuk, Finalising of data entry and checking, back-ups etc
30th of September 2024	Arrival in Nuuk at 10:00

1.4 Survey area

Figure 1: Map of proposed sampling area on the east coast of Greenland

2. Geomorphology

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2.1 Equipment

RV Tarajoq is equipped with a multibeam Teledyne RESON SeaBat 7160 (operating at freq. 44 kHz) and sub-bottom profiler Innomar SES-2000 Medium-100 (operating at freq. 12 kHz); Applanix POSMV OceanMaster.

2.2 Summary

Multibeam echo sounder (MBES) data were collected continuously throughout the survey (day and night) and during transit to and from harbors. Exception to this were stops at the sampling stations to avoid excess of noise in the water column during drift. The readings and measurements from MBES were the primary source of depth and subsea landscape information to navigators, crew, and scientists during all operations. Sound velocity profiles were periodically collected alongside CTD measurements in the project area to correct the effect of sonar beam refraction due to water density changes. MBES logging was accompanied by sub-bottom profiler (SBP) data recorded at selected stations, where multicorer was deployed to aid the search for soft bottom, as well as to validate the final stratigraphic interpretations. Positioning and movements of the vessel were calculated directly with the Applanix POSMV v5 OceanMaster (SN 11262) receiving data from an Inertial Motion Unit and two Trimble GNSS 540 AP antennas. The Applanix POSMV is the main source of vessel inertia, GNSS (GPS) position and time synchronization information for all sonars. Detailed survey information together with example images of POSMV and GNSS positioning can be found in Appendix 1 (see below).

The total area mapped during the Deep Trace cruise is 1941,47937 km² (Figure 1 and 2.1).

Figure 2.1 shows a 2D map and 3D model of multibeam tracks (color grid) of the project area together with all sampled CTD stations (cross symbol). Color scale represents water depth. The total area mapped is 1941,47937 km².

The collected MBES and SBP datasets will deliver new knowledge on seafloor terrain features, underwater landforms, sediment types, and possibly geological units in the area off South-East Greenland. The surveyed project area comprised of 3 transects and spanned from the shallow banks and deep-water troughs to continental slope and deep-sea basin, covering a high topographic complexity and a large variety of benthic habitats. In the coastal region, seafloor data reveal a highly rugged terrain with numerous crisscrossing tunnels suggesting bedrock exposed at the surface (likely Archaean basement) and sculpted by the glacial processes. Further offshore, the landscape transforms into deep-water troughs down to c. 1000 m and continued rugged terrain structure. Streamlined glacial landforms are present particularly in the deeper parts of northernmost and middle transects, reminiscent of past glacial flow (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2 shows example glacial lineation (crag-and-tails) in transect 1.

The middle and southernmost transects displayed a surprising presence of gravelly and rocky sediments in deeper basins and troughs, possibly due to a strong activity of oceanic current, flushing soft sediments. The offshore continental shelf area was comprised of vast plains, which transition into continental slope, characterized by deep canyons (Figure 2.3), most likely carved by glacial meltwater outflow following the Last Glacial Maximum (around

20,000 years ago). In addition, some interesting single mounds and crater-like features were found between Iceland and Greenland in deep sea region during transit.

Figure 2.3 shows deep canyons off the continental slope off East Greenland.

The collected seafloor data will be analyzed in detail for morphological classes and geological features in the area. In combination with other collected data, such as video footage of benthic communities and habitat types, we will produce a spatial benthic habitat model, following the protocol described in Krawczyk et al. (2021)

2.3 Data Storage/Availability

All MBES and SBP data collected during the Deep Trace cruise in September 2024 are stored at the GINR database, i.e. multibeam data as .qpd, .xyz, .asc, and .tiff formats, shallow seismic data as .ses3 format. All MBES positional data will be processed against DGPS information from base stations on land using QPS Qinertia or PosPAC MMS 8 for higher accuracy in three dimensions, and to adapt to Mean Sea Level of Greenland on the ggeoid16 geoid from The Danish National Mapping Agency and DTU Space.

Automatically and manually processed multibeam bathymetry data will be submitted to the Danish Geodata Agency (Geodatastyrelsen) and they will be further gridded to a 100-meter resolution grid (.geotiff format) and submitted to the International Bathymetric Chart of the Arctic Ocean (IBCAO) under the IHO Nippon Foundation Seabed 2030 for open access.

Table 2.1. Survey information of the project area

Variable	Information
Number of MBES files	157 files (25 GB)
Number of SBP files	178 files (37 GB)
Number of SVP files	23 files
Total area mapped	1941,47937 km ²
Acquisition software	QPS Qinsy 8.4.4
Positioning software	Applanix MV-PosView 11.21
Datum	Datum : WGS 84 (Greenwich) Spheroid name : WGS 84
Projection	Projection name : Universal Transverse Mercator (North Hemisphere) UTM zone number : 24 EPSG: 32624
Mean Water Level Model	None
Height above draft	5.440 m
Geometry TX MBES	X (Stbd = Positive) : -0.463 m Y (Bow = Positive) : 6.747 m Z (Up = Positive) : -16.877 m A-priori SD : 0.005 m Heading offset : 1.634 ° Roll offset : -0.085 ° Pitch offset : 1.628 °

Geometry RX MBES - RX	X (Stbd = Positive): : -0.461 m Y (Bow = Positive): : 7.730 m Z (Up = Positive): : -16.806 m A-priori SD : 0.005 m Heading offset : 1.224 ° Roll offset : -0.005 ° Pitch offset : 2.038 °
Geometry IMU	Lever Arms...: Ref. to IMU Target, 0 0 0, IMU Frame wrt Ref Frame: -0.390, -0.130, 0.040; Target to Sensing centre: 0.000, 0.001, 0.086, Resulting Lever Arm: 0.000, 0.002, 0.086; Ref to P. GNSS Lever Arm: -10.143, 1.226, -12.650 Ref to Vessel Lever Arm: 0.000, 0.000, 0.000 Ref to Centre of Rotation Lever Arm: -16.468, -0.504, 9.331
Other MBES information	Beam angle width along : 1.500 ° Beam angle width across : 1.500 ° Maximum number of beams per ping : 512

Example image

3. Benthic Ecosystem

3.1 Benthic imagery

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3.1.1 Objective

The majority of knowledge on epibenthic deep-sea communities from Greenland is being derived from the GINR based bycatch monitoring programme. However, this is based on a sampling method designed to assess the health of commercial fish stocks rather than provide an understanding of the benthic ecosystem and often avoids geomorphological complex habitat features. A customised benthic video sledge was used to study benthic communities along a gradient from the coast along a deep trench towards the shelf edge and at the bottom of the shelf slope. This will give better insights into, shallow coastal communities, which are often not part of the traditional fisheries survey, provide information of typical communities encountered across the East Greenland shelf and their geomorphological drivers and improve our understanding of benthic communities on rarely sampled shelf slopes

3.1.2 Video sledge deployment procedure

The custom made GINR owned video sledge (design by R. Nygaard) was equipped with two GoPro Hero5 cameras in GroupBinc housings, two GroupBinc GPH2-1750M LED torches, a Marport Trawl Eye Explorer (see Figure 3.1.1 B) and custom-made laser block featuring 4 green Quadro Laser Scale 150 (532nm wavelength). These were arranged in form of a quadrat with all midpoints exactly 15cm apart. The camera taking a continuous video was mounted centrally and at an oblique angle (27°) on the sledge 48 cm above the seabed and parallel to the lasers. This resulted in a laserpoint distance off 334mm vertically and 150mm horizontally, when the sledge sat on the seabed. The second camera, taking pictures at an interval of 1 second, was placed centrally at an angle of 180° and allowed for top-view pictures of the epibenthos. Customised underwater GroupBinc video lights were placed on either side of the video camera, angled inwards to achieve the most even illumination possible without backscattering caused by particles in the water column.

The video sledge was deployed at each site once and towed along the seabed for 20 minutes. Marport data to collect information about pitch and roll, depth, and speed were logged at 2-minute intervals, starting from the moment the video sledge reached the seabed

and was fully stabilized. A list of all deployments can be found in table 3.1.1 and Figure 3.1.1 A.

Figure 3.1.1: A) Realised stations, B) Video sledge used for recording epibenthic communities, equipped with two cameras, LED-lights, laser and a Marport for data logging.

Table 3.1.1: Sampling details for each station

Event Nr.	Station	Date	Lat. Start	Long. Start	Lat. End	Long. End	Depth Start	Depth End	Bottom Temp.
7	OT1_6	20. Sep 24	64.3118500	37.5712333	64.31503334	37.56336664	731	745	4.3
9	OT1_5	20. Sep 24	64.5797833	38.05045	64.57820002	38.06168333	658	664	4.4
24	OT1_1	21. Sep 24	65.4893166	38.31016668	65.48888334	38.30158332	441	378	4.61
25	OT1_2	21. Sep 24	65.24355	38.31863333	65.24623334	38.31576665	450	454	4.8
28	OT1_3	21. Sep 24	64.9827833	38.30754999	64.98295002	38.30068334	798	796	4.4

31	OT1_4	22. Sep 24	64.77 12166 5	38.276 98332	64.774 91665	38.279 51667	687	682	4.4
35	OT1_7	22. Sep 24	64.15 51833 3	37.024 05	64.155 55	37.018 01667	422	428	4.49
38	OT1_8	22. Sep 24	64.04 87333 3	36.635 46664	64.048 28333	36.625 26665	358	362	4.6
41	OT1_9	22. Sep 24	63.92 83666 6	36.204 6	63.929 50001	36.203 63334	1358	1354	3.5
47	OT2_8	23. Sep 24	63.25 33	39.481 33332	63.256 96667	39.489 78332	1236	1089	3.73
56	OT2_4	24. Sep 24	63.73 85166 8	40.095 16667	63.741 55	40.093 95	932	914	5.1
61	OT2_2	24. Sep 24	63.98 42666 6	40.268 88332	63.987 60001	40.261 11666	1033	1037	5.3
64	OT2_1	24. Sep 24	64.22 34499 9	40.256 81667	64.225 91667	40.244 06667	152	163	2.51
70	OT2_3	25. Sep 24	63.87 83833 2	40.225 73333	63.881 58334	40.222 23333	947	976	5
71	OT2_4	25. Sep 24	64.73 22666 8	40.093 25	64.735 68331	40.095 65	855	879	5.1
75	OT2_5	25. Sep 24	63.66 99499 8	39.958 18335	63.673 46668	39.963 15002	575	599	5.1
76	OT2_6	25. Sep 24	63.56 93499 9	39.754 99999	63.574 06667	39.759 18331	546	548	5.1
84	OT3_6	26. Sep 24	62.21 51	40.418 85001	62.217 18334	40.417 25	1264	1262	3.9
87	OT3_5	26. Sep 24	62.25 70500 1	40.549 60003	62.260 20001	40.545 81668	392	385	5.5
92	OT3_4	26. Sep 24	62.32 27833 4	40.882 78332	62.325 01666	40.891 50003	649	654	5.4

95	OT3_3	26. Sep 24	62.41 04000 1	41.282 13332	62.414 85001	41.286 69999	502	519	5.4
100	OT3_1	27. Sep 24	62.59 02833 3	42.005 36667	62.593 66665	42.000 1	319	291	3.35
103	OT3_2	27. Sep 24	62.50 43833 4	41.687 93335	62.507 73335	41.688 31666	335	359	4.4
79	OT2_7	25. Sep 24	63.39 97000 1	39.560 53333	63.402 78333	39.565 41665	399	396	5.1

3.1.3 Preliminary findings

On preliminary viewings we could already see a noteworthy difference between taxa associated with shallow, coastal stations and deep stations on the shelf and those on the shelf slope. Shallow coastal sites were often rocky featuring a fine mud veneer and were dominated by crinoids or sponges, such as station OT2_1 (Figure 3.1.2). Deep stations in glacially derived trenches on the shelf were either comprised of typical mud communities or, in case of hard substratum such as bedrock or moraines were colonised by dense sponge assemblages. One video along the shelf edge was taken within and outside an old iceberg scour and on first viewings revealed similar communities between both, indicating that this may have been an old scouring mark. The shelf slope featured distinctly different communities than those found on the shelf both in abundance and identity. Mushroom corals, for example, were observed in all three shelf slope stations but never on the deep stations on the shelf (Figure 3.1.3).

All images will be processed and analysed at GINR. Epifaunal richness and community composition within and between sites will be analysed with respect to substratum type, depth, and corresponding environmental variables.

Figure 3.1.2: High crinoid densities observed at shallow coastal station OT2_1 (event nr. 64) at a depth of 152m.

Figure 3.1.3: Typical benthic community types found on the A) shelf slope (Station OT1_9) at a depth of 1358m featuring mushroom and other soft corals, B) on a moraine (Station OT2_4) showing a typical sponge assemblage at a depth of 932m, and C) within a glacially formed basin, featuring a muddy habitat type (Station OT3_4) at a depth of 649m.

3.1.4 Data quality notes/problems

There were no significant sample collection or data quality concerns to note. However, due to the nature of the video sled being dragged along the seabed, clashes with large boulders would result in minor camera angle shifts towards the ground. A calibration plate was used on the laser beams both before deployment and after the retrieval of the sled to adjust for such possible changes, and with the help of the ship engineers the holding mechanism for the laser and camera block has been improved using a grab-screw drilled through the camera holder, helping to stabilize the camera when bumping into boulders on the seabed. To improve and accelerate deployments, release lines were used towards the end of the cruise to stabilize the video sled whilst sliding into the water from the trawl deck to minimize collision of the sled with the ship which was resulting in shifts of the camera angle. The laser and camera block was manually readjusted after each deployment. While each station was successfully visited once, station OT2_4 was visited twice, due to the

laser resurfacing loose after the first deployment. Initially the sledge was lowered with 40m/s. with a real battery life of 1 h, this proved too long for the deep shelf slope stations. Thus, only images were collected for station OT1_9. Lowering speed of the videosled was consequently adjusted to 60m/s to ensure successful video collection. During data curation, data files for both videos and pictures from sites OT1_3, OTI_8 were lost owing to mismanagement of data back-ups. Subsequently a clearer data management protocol was established for the rest of the cruise.

3.2 Epibenthic diversity and abundance

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3.2.1 Introduction & Objectives:

The project aim is to study benthic habitats that have so far remained understudied and are of potential high conservation value. Such an area is found around Tasiilaq (East Greenland), where the densest cover of hard corals on the eastern Greenland shelf has been found so far. This project aims to better understand the seabed ecosystem of the East Greenland shelf.

The Deep-Trace cruise, in particular, focused on the study of gradients in benthic epifaunal communities from the coast to the shelf break, taking into account large geomorphological features such as the deep trench just in front of Tasiilaq.

The main objectives for the collection of beamtrawl data were

- Collect data from beam trawls in order to gain better knowledge and insights of the benthic epifauna in the area and establish a clearer link between communities observed on videos at the same station.
- Collect algae fragments to understand macroalgal carbon export to sequestration habitats within Greenland as part of another existing project (BlueCea).

3.2.2 Methodology:

The study area of this cruise is the East Greenland shelf, between 65.8°N and 63.6°N, in front and south of Tasiilaq (Figure 3.2.1).

At all epibenthic stations a beam trawl was deployed (Figure 3.2.2a). The beam trawl opening is 2.52 m with a 10 mm mesh size in the cod-end. Tow duration on the seabed was 6 minutes at a speed of 1.2 knots (List of station in Table 3.2.1).

Upon recovery, the trawl was opened above a large 1 mm sieve, cleaned with seawater if necessary and partially sorted for big and rare species (Figure 3.2.2b). Sampling was carried out following the Standard Operating Procedures for the benthic bycatch monitoring programme to aid later integration of the data.

Figure 3.2.1: Realised beamtrawl stations

If/when rocks or big sponges were in the net, they were removed first, ensuring no organisms were on them. Rocks were discarded and sponges identified and weighed. Then the sample was emptied onto the big sieve and processed as described above.

After initial sorting the sample were further processed in the laboratory. If samples were estimated too big to be processed as a whole, a subsample was taken and the total weight and subsample weight were registered in the GINR database.

Figure 3.2.2: a) beam trawl on the deck; b) sample emptied in the sieve.

Samples were sorted, separating all the different morphotaxa present in different trays (Figure 3.2.3). A photography was taken of each sorted sample. Taxa were then identified to the lowest taxonomic level possible, counted and weighed. Data were entered in the Greenlandic Institute of Natural Resources database (List of encountered taxa in Table 3.2.2).

DNA samples were collected for some coral species. Molluscs have been collected for a specialist working on molluscs taxonomy. Interesting specimens have been fixed in ethanol 96%.

Figure 3.2.3: sorted taxa from a station.

3.2.3 Preliminary observations:

The beam trawl was deployed at a total of 12 stations at depth varying between 150 and 1400 m deep. Shallow stations were the richest in term of biodiversity and abundances. While deeper stations showed lower number in both biodiversity and abundance. Sponges were present in almost all stations, although identification was made extremely difficult as a result of the sponges being fragmented during the trawling. At the shallowest station, station OT2_1, the crinoids (Echinodermata) were the dominant taxa.

At deepest stations, St. 43 (1040 m), St. 80 (1290 m) and St. 119 (1400 m) some deep-sea organisms were collected. Among those interesting specimen, two genus of the so-called mushroom soft coral (Octocorallia: Alcyonacea: Alcyoniidae) *Anthomastus* sp and

Pseudoanthomastus sp (Figure 3.2.4a,b) were found. The latter has a known association with a scale worm, living in the fold of the rim. *Pseudoanthomastus sp* was collected at stations 43 and 80 and *Anthomastus sp* at station 80. A stalked crinoid, *Rhizocrinus lofotensis* has also been collected at station 80 (Figure 3.2.5a,b), as well as a very small ophiuroid, *Ophiotjalfa vivipara* (Figure 3.2.6a). This is a very small species whose central disk diameter reaches 5 mm. *Ophiotjalfa vivipara* has been collected for the first time in East Greenland (Martynov & Litvinova, 2008). It has been found at the two deepest stations St. 80 and St. 119. Additionally, at St. 80 an unidentified bryozoa (Cheilostomata, Figure 3.2.6b) has been collected and has been preserved for further identification by experts. Specimen of the stalked crinoid and the ophiuroid have also been fixed in ethanol for the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources collection.

Figure 3.2.4: a) *Anthomastus sp.*; b) *Pseudoanthomastus sp.* and associated scale worm.

Figure 3.2.5: *Rhizocrinus lofotensis* a) stalk; b) calyx.

Figure 3.2.6: a) *Ophiotjalfa vivipara*; b) unidentified bryozoa.

Table3.2.1: Beam trawl stations list

Gear	Year	Ship	Trip	Station	Fix Pos	Start latitude decimal	Start longitude decimal	End latitude decimal	End longitude decimal	TimeStart	TimeEnd	Depth1	Depth2	Fishing depth2	Fishing Depth2	T °
BEAM	2024	TA	6	3	OT1_7	64.17031666	37.08835	64.17136666	37.09303333	02:04	02:10	429	431	429	433	4,3
BEAM	2024	TA	6	13	OT1_4	64.7728	38.24290001	64.77020003	38.2467	20:13	20:23	632	639	632	643	4,2
BEAM	2024	TA	6	15	OT1_2	65.24183334	38.31761665	65.24393333	38.31711667	02:43	02:49	453	452	451	453	4,6
BEAM	2024	TA	6	43	OT1_9	63.9278333	36.26855001	63.92606665	36.27038333	02:06	02:12	1038	1048	1038	1048	3,8
BEAM	2024	TA	6	49	OT2_7	63.38788335	39.56781667	63.38658333	39.57049999	18:25	18:31	404	402	400	404	4,9
BEAM	2024	TA	6	52	OT2_4	63.70900002	40.16648334	63.70913334	40.16748333	02:30	02:37	752	762	751	762	
BEAM	2024	TA	6	65	OT2_1	64.23568333	40.22516667	64.23723334	40.22303333	20:14	20:20	151	156	150	156	1,8
BEAM	2024	TA	6	80	OT2_8	63.20249999	39.75708332	63.20423333	39.75543334	21:16	21:22	1287	1293	1282	1293	3,7
BEAM	2024	TA	6	97	OT3_3	62.42283335	41.25503333	62.42489999	41.22183334	22:05	22:11	517	514	514	517	5,2
BEAM	2024	TA	6	98	OT3_1	62.58056666	42.02905	62.57999999	42.02496667	02:16	02:22	274	271	271	275	3
BEAM	2024	TA	6	109	OT3_5	62.24371667	40.5699	62.24536667	40.57186667	19:51	19:57	406	408	404	408	5,5
BEAM	2024	TA	6	112	OT3_6	62.18388333	40.41378333	62.18503334	40.41001666	01:43	01:49	1410	1409	1409	1412	3,5

Table3.2.2: List of taxa identified during the cruise, for all the beam trawls with classification and frequency of encounter.

AphiaID_ accepted	Scientific Name <i>accepted</i>	King- dom	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Sub- genus	Species	Freq
130081	<i>Euphrosine borealis</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Amphinomida	Euphrosinidae	Euphrosine		borealis	1
157381	<i>Euphrosine cirrata</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Amphinomida	Euphrosinidae	Euphrosine		cirrata	1
129285	<i>Euphrosine</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Amphinomida	Euphrosinidae	Euphrosine			1
967	<i>Lumbrineridae</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae				2
965	<i>Onuphidae</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Onuphidae				2
157181	<i>Aphrodita hastata</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Aphroditidae	Aphroditella		hastata	1
129844	<i>Laetmonice filicornis</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Aphroditidae	Laetmonice		filicornis	8
129300	<i>Goniada</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Goniadidae	Goniada			1
129370	<i>Nephtys</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nephtyidae	Nephtys			1
130745	<i>Eunoe nodosa</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	Eunoe		nodosa	4
129491	<i>Harmothoe</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	Harmothoe			1
939	<i>Polynoidae</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae				6
985	<i>Sabellidae</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae				5
131025	<i>Placostegus tridentatus</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	Placostegus		tridentatus	2
988	<i>Serpulidae</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae				3
982	<i>Terebellidae</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae				5

129220	<i>Notomastus</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta		Capitellidae	Notomastus			1
130277	<i>Chirimia biceps</i>	Animalia	Annelida	Polychaeta		Maldanidae	Chirimia		biceps	1
175027	<i>Golfingia (Golfingia) margaritacea</i>	Animalia	Annelida		Sipuncula	Golfingiidae	Golfingia	Golfingia	margaritacea	1
136025	<i>Phascolion</i>	Animalia	Annelida		Sipuncula	Golfingiidae	Phascolion			1
101958	<i>Haploops tubicola</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	Haploops		tubicola	1
101447	<i>Haploops</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	Haploops			1
102152	<i>Paramphithoe hystrix</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Paramphithoidae	Paramphithoe		hystrix	1
102945	<i>Pardalisca abyssi</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Pardaliscidae	Pardalisca		abyssi	1
1135	<i>Amphipoda</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda					1
107581	<i>Acanthephyra pelagica</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Acanthephyridae	Acanthephyra		pelagica	1
107021	<i>Hymenodora</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Acanthephyridae	Hymenodora			1
107563	<i>Pontophilus norvegicus</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Crangonidae	Pontophilus		norvegicus	5
107568	<i>Sclerocrangon boreas</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Crangonidae	Sclerocrangon		boreas	1
107316	<i>Dorhynchus thomsoni</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Inachidae	Dorhynchus		thomsoni	1
107166	<i>Munida tenuimana</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Munididae	Munida		tenuimana	1
106835	<i>Munida</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Munididae	Munida			1
158351	<i>Atlantopandalus propinquus</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	Atlantopandalus		propinquus	3
107649	<i>Pandalus borealis</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	Pandalus		borealis	2

158351	<i>Atlantopandalus propinquus</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	Pandalus		propinquus	3
107678	<i>Pasiphaea tarda</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pasiphaeidae	Pasiphaea		tarda	1
107521	<i>Lebbeus polaris</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Thoridae	Lebbeus		polaris	4
106989	<i>Lebbeus</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Thoridae	Lebbeus			1
118814	<i>Aegiochus arctica</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Aegidae	Aegiochus		arctica	2
118831	<i>Aegiochus ventrosa</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Aegidae	Aegiochus		ventrosa	2
119930	<i>Gnathophausia zoea</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Lophogastrida	Gnathophausiidae	Gnathophausia		zoea	3
134654	<i>Pseudopallene brevicollis</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Callipallenidae	Pseudopallene		brevicollis	1
134669	<i>Colossendeis proboscidea</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Colossendeidae	Colossendeis		proboscidea	1
134686	<i>Nymphon elegans</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Nymphonidae	Nymphon		elegans	1
134690	<i>Nymphon hirtipes</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Nymphonidae	Nymphon		hirtipes	6
134711	<i>Nymphon stroemi</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Nymphonidae	Nymphon		stroemi	2
134591	<i>Nymphon</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Nymphonidae	Nymphon			3
1566	<i>Nymphonidae</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Nymphonidae				1
106182	<i>Arcoscalpellum michelottianum</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Thecostraca	Scalpellomorpha	Scalpellidae	Arcoscalpellum		michelottianum	1
1424477	<i>Weltnerium stroemii</i>	Animalia	Arthropoda	Thecostraca	Scalpellomorpha	Scalpellidae	Ornatoscalpellum		stroemii	2
235385	<i>Novocrania anomala</i>	Animalia	Brachiopoda	Craniata	Craniida	Craniidae	Novocrania		anomala	1
104040	<i>Terebratulina</i>	Animalia	Brachiopoda	Rhynchonellata	Terebratulida	Cancellothyrididae	Terebratulina			2

104062	<i>Macandrevia cranium</i>	Animalia	Brachiopoda	Rhynchonellata	Terebratulida	Zeileriidae	Macandrevia		cranium	1
104046	<i>Macandrevia</i>	Animalia	Brachiopoda	Rhynchonellata	Terebratulida	Zeileriidae	Macandrevia			1
110831	<i>Cystisella</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Bryocryptellidae	Cystisella			1
110835	<i>Porella</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Bryocryptellidae	Porella			1
111230	<i>Caberea ellisii</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Candidae	Caberea		ellisii	2
110866	<i>Scrupocellaria</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Candidae	Scrupocellaria			1
111268	<i>Cellepora pumicosa</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Celleporidae	Cellepora		pumicosa	1
110873	<i>Cellepora</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Celleporidae	Cellepora			1
110875	<i>Celleporina</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Celleporidae	Celleporina			1
110911	<i>Flustra</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Flustridae	Flustra			1
111373	<i>Sarsiflustra abyssicola</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Flustridae	Sarsiflustra		abyssicola	2
465722	<i>Serratiflustra serrulata</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Flustridae	Serratiflustra		serrulata	1
986944	<i>Terminoflustra barleei</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Flustridae	Terminoflustra		barleei	8
110765	<i>Myriaporidae</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Myriaporidae				2
110956	<i>Reteporella</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Phidoloporidae	Reteporella			8
110836	<i>Rhamphostomella</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Umbonulidae	Rhamphostomella			1
110722	<i>Cheilostomatida</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida					1
110993	<i>Alcyonidium</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Ctenostomatida	Alcyonidiidae	Alcyonidium			1
111032	<i>Crisia</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Stenolaemata	Cyclostomatida	Crisiidae	Crisia			1
111723	<i>Hornera lichenoides</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Stenolaemata	Cyclostomatida	Horneridae	Hornera		lichenoides	5

111041	<i>Hornera</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Stenolaemata	Cyclostomatida	Horneridae	Hornera			7
470799	<i>Diplosolen intricarium</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Stenolaemata	Cyclostomatida	Plagioeciidae	Diplosolen		intricarium	2
111052	<i>Idmidronea</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa	Stenolaemata	Cyclostomatida	Tubuliporidae	Idmidronea			4
146142	<i>Bryozoa</i>	Animalia	Bryozoa							3
103456	<i>Didemnum</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Didemnidae	Didemnum			6
103439	<i>Didemnidae</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Didemnidae				1
103624	<i>Eudistoma vitreum</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Polycitoridae	Eudistoma		vitreum	1
103434	<i>Aplousobranchia</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia					1
103483	<i>Ascidia</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Asciidiidae	Ascidia			2
103488	<i>Ciona</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Cionidae	Ciona			1
103509	<i>Molgula</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Molgulidae	Molgula			1
103531	<i>Dendrodoa</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Styelidae	Dendrodoa			1
103893	<i>Kukenthalia borealis</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Styelidae	Kukenthalia		borealis	2
1839	<i>Ascidiacea</i>	Animalia	Chordata	Ascidiacea						1
100954	<i>Hormathia nodosa</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Hormathiidae	Hormathia		nodosa	1
1360	<i>Actiniaria</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria					3
117093	<i>Eudendrium</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Anthoathecata	Eudendriidae	Eudendrium			1
117246	<i>Stylaster</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Anthoathecata	Stylasteridae	Stylaster			1
22805	<i>Stylasteridae</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Anthoathecata	Stylasteridae				1
744825	<i>Aglaophenopsis bonnevieae</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Aglaopheniidae	Aglaophenopsis		bonnevieae	1

744828	<i>Aglaophenopsis cornuta</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Aglaopheniidae	Aglaophenopsis		cornuta	1
117293	<i>Cladocarpus formosus</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Aglaopheniidae	Cladocarpus		formosus	1
117294	<i>Cladocarpus integer</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Aglaopheniidae	Cladocarpus		integer	2
117000	<i>Cladocarpus</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Aglaopheniidae	Cladocarpus			1
117103	<i>Halecium</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Haleciidae	Halecium			3
117692	<i>Grammaria abietina</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Lafoeidae	Grammaria		abietina	1
117809	<i>Nemertesia antennina</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Plumulariidae	Nemertesia		antennina	2
117195	<i>Nemertesia</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Plumulariidae	Nemertesia			1
158196	<i>Thuiaria laxa</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Sertulariidae	Thuiaria		laxa	1
117237	<i>Thuiaria</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Sertulariidae	Thuiaria			1
1614	<i>Sertulariidae</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Sertulariidae				4
125269	<i>Alcyoniidae</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Alcyoniidae				2
146941	<i>Drifa glomerata</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Capnellidae	Drifa		glomerata	1
146940	<i>Drifa</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Capnellidae	Drifa			1
290873	<i>Pseudodrifa groenlandica</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Capnellidae	Pseudodrifa		groenlandica	1
267775	<i>Pseudodrifa</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Capnellidae	Pseudodrifa			1
125285	<i>Anthomastus</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Coralliidae	Anthomastus			1
135282	<i>Atolla wyvillei</i>	Animalia	Cnidaria	Scyphozoa	Coronatae	Atollidae	Atolla		wyvillei	2
123213	<i>Novodinia</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Brisingida	Novodiniidae	Novodinia			1

123796	<i>Icasterias panopla</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Forcipulatida	Asteriidae	Icasterias		panopla	2
123896	<i>Leptychaster arcticus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Astropectinidae	Leptychaster		arcticus	1
123915	<i>Ctenodiscus crispatus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Ctenodiscidae	Ctenodiscus		crispatus	1
123276	<i>Henricia</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Spinulosida	Echinasteridae	Henricia			11
124002	<i>Tremaster mirabilis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Asterinidae	Tremaster		mirabilis	1
124020	<i>Ceramaster granularis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Goniasteridae	Ceramaster		granularis	2
125170	<i>Poraniomorpha (Poraniomorpha) hispida</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Poraniidae	Poraniomorpha	Poraniomorpha	hispida	7
124155	<i>Crossaster squamatus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Solasteridae	Crossaster		squamatus	2
123336	<i>Crossaster</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Solasteridae	Crossaster			1
124163	<i>Solaster glacialis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Solasteridae	Solaster		glacialis	1
124167	<i>Solaster syrtensis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Solasteridae	Solaster		syrtensis	2
124126	<i>Myxaster sol</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Velatida	Myxasteridae	Myxaster		sol	1
124128	<i>Diplopteraster multipes</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Velatida	Pterasteridae	Diplopteraster		multipes	1
124135	<i>Hymenaster pellucidus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Velatida	Pterasteridae	Hymenaster		pellucidus	1
124147	<i>Pteraster militaris</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Velatida	Pterasteridae	Pteraster		militaris	1
124151	<i>Pteraster pulvillus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Velatida	Pterasteridae	Pteraster		pulvillus	3
124223	<i>Heliometra glacialis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Crinoidea	Comatulida	Antedonidae	Heliometra		glacialis	1
124229	<i>Poliometra proluxa</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Crinoidea	Comatulida	Antedonidae	Poliometra		proluxa	5

124188	<i>Rhizocrinus lofotensis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Crinoidea	Comatulida	Rhizocrinidae	Conocrinus		lofotensis	1
124188	<i>Rhizocrinus lofotensis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Crinoidea	Comatulida	Rhizocrinidae	Rhizocrinus		lofotensis	1
123081	<i>Crinoidea</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Crinoidea						1
532031	<i>Gracilechinus acutus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Echinoidea	Camarodonta	Echinidae	Gracilechinus		acutus	1
532035	<i>Gracilechinus elegans</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Echinoidea	Camarodonta	Echinidae	Gracilechinus		elegans	1
411391	<i>Gracilechinus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Echinoidea	Camarodonta	Echinidae	Gracilechinus			1
123160	<i>Echinidae</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Echinoidea	Camarodonta	Echinidae				2
123390	<i>Strongylocentrotus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Echinoidea	Camarodonta	Strongylocentrotidae	Strongylocentrotus			2
124404	<i>Brisaster fragilis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Echinoidea	Spatangoida	Schizasteridae	Brisaster		fragilis	6
123441	<i>Myriotrochus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Holothuroidea	Apodida	Myriotrochidae	Myriotrochus			1
124756	<i>Laetmogone violacea</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Holothuroidea	Elasipodida	Laetmogonidae	Laetmogone		violacea	4
124798	<i>Molpadia borealis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Holothuroidea	Molpadida	Molpadiidae	Molpadia		borealis	1
125126	<i>Ophiopus arcticus</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphilepidida incertae sedis	Ophiopus		arcticus	2
123613	<i>Amphiura</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	Amphiura			2
125109	<i>Ophiactis abyssicola</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Ophiactidae	Ophiactis		abyssicola	7
125125	<i>Ophiopholis aculeata</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Ophiopholidae	Ophiopholis		aculeata	8
124973	<i>Ophiacantha abyssicola</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiacanthidae	Ophiacantha		abyssicola	2
1574967	<i>Ophiosabine anomala</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiacanthidae	Ophiacantha		anomala	4

124978	<i>Ophiacantha bidentata</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiacanthidae	Ophiacantha		bidentata	4
1589844	<i>Ophiosemmotes clavigera</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiacanthidae	Ophiomitrella		clavigera	3
123209	<i>Ophiomyxidae</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiomyxidae				1
125147	<i>Ophioscolex glacialis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophioscolecida	Ophioscolecidae	Ophioscolex		glacialis	8
123633	<i>Ophioscolex</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophioscolecida	Ophioscolecidae	Ophioscolex			1
183315	<i>Ophiopleura inermis</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	Ophiopyrgidae	Ophiopleura		inermis	4
124860	<i>Ophiocten sericeum</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	Ophiuridae	Ophiocten		sericeum	1
123561	<i>Ophiocten</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	Ophiuridae	Ophiocten			1
124933	<i>Ophiura robusta</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	Ophiuridae	Ophiura		robusta	1
124934	<i>Ophiura sarsii</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	Ophiuridae	Ophiura		sarsii	5
123200	<i>Ophiuridae</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	Ophiuridae				1
123084	<i>Ophiuroidea</i>	Animalia	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea						2
138796	<i>Bathyarca frielei</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Arcidae	Bathyarca		frielei	1
138797	<i>Bathyarca glacialis</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Arcidae	Bathyarca		glacialis	1
137673	<i>Bathyarca</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Arcidae	Bathyarca			3
1765892	<i>Paracratis minuta</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Limopsidae	Limopsis		minuta	2
138820	<i>Astarte crenata</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Carditida	Astartidae	Astarte		crenata	2
137683	<i>Astarte</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Carditida	Astartidae	Astarte			4
253	<i>Teredinidae</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myida	Teredinidae				1

140702	<i>Delectopecten vitreus</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Pectinidae	Delectopecten		vitreus	1
140700	<i>Cyclopecten hoskynsi</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Propeamussiidae	Cyclopecten		hoskynsi	2
137858	<i>Cuspidaria</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Bivalvia		Cuspidariidae	Cuspidaria			1
140596	<i>Bathypolypus arcticus</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Cephalopoda	Octopoda	Bathypolypodidae	Bathypolypus		arcticus	3
157019	<i>Graneledone verrucosa</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Cephalopoda	Octopoda	Megaleledonidae	Graneledone		verrucosa	1
138036	<i>Gonatus</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Cephalopoda	Oegopsida	Gonatidae	Gonatus			2
138481	<i>Rossia</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Cephalopoda	Sepiida	Sepiolidae	Rossia			1
143	<i>Velutinidae</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Velutinidae				1
160143	<i>Buccinum finmarkianum</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Buccinidae	Buccinum		finmarkianum	1
138906	<i>Colus sabini</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Colidae	Colus		sabini	1
137714	<i>Turrisipho</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Colidae	Turrisipho			1
137793	<i>Clione</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Pteropoda	Clionidae	Clione			1
140187	<i>Lepeta caeca</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Gastropoda		Lepetidae	Lepeta		caeca	1
140082	<i>Hanleya hanleyi</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Polyplacophora	Lepidopleurida	Hanleyidae	Hanleya		hanleyi	2
138058	<i>Hanleya</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Polyplacophora	Lepidopleurida	Hanleyidae	Hanleya			1
202	<i>Dentaliidae</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Scaphopoda	Dentaliida	Dentaliidae				1
104	<i>Scaphopoda</i>	Animalia	Mollusca	Scaphopoda						1
152391	<i>Nemertea</i>	Animalia	Nemertea							3
131729	<i>Clathrina</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Calcarea	Clathrinida	Clathrinidae	Clathrina			1
131593	<i>Clathrinida</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Calcarea	Clathrinida					1

131616	<i>Leucosoleniidae</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Calcarea	Leucosolenida	Leucosoleniidae				1
131723	<i>Sycon</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Calcarea	Leucosolenida	Syconidae	Sycon			2
132510	<i>Phakellia rugosa</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Axinellida	Axinellidae	Axinella		rugosa	2
131629	<i>Axinellidae</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Axinellida	Axinellidae				10
163084	<i>Axinellida</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Axinellida					1
132509	<i>Phakellia robusta</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Bubarida	Bubaridae	Phakellia		robusta	2
132510	<i>Phakellia rugosa</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Bubarida	Bubaridae	Phakellia		rugosa	1
132511	<i>Phakellia ventilabrum</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Bubarida	Bubaridae	Phakellia		ventilabrum	3
131779	<i>Phakellia</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Bubarida	Bubaridae	Phakellia			1
132972	<i>Iophon piceum</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Acaridae	Iophon		piceum	2
131893	<i>Asbestopluma</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Cladorhizidae	Asbestopluma			2
863519	<i>Lycopodina</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Cladorhizidae	Lycopodina			1
131921	<i>Forcepia</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Coelosphaeridae	Forcepia			6
131925	<i>Histodermella</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Coelosphaeridae	Histodermella			1
131950	<i>Hymedesmia</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Hymedesmiidae	Hymedesmia			7
131655	<i>Hymedesmiidae</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Hymedesmiidae				1
167882	<i>Antho (Antho) dichotoma</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Microcionidae	Antho	Antho	dichotoma	2
168640	<i>Mycale (Mycale) lingua</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Mycalidae	Mycale	Mycale	lingua	5
168642	<i>Mycale (Mycale) loveni</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Mycalidae	Mycale	Mycale	loveni	1

131907	<i>Mycale</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Mycalidae	Mycale			2
133868	<i>Melonanchora elliptica</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Myxillidae	Melonanchora		elliptica	1
157415	<i>Polymastia andrica</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Polymastiida	Polymastiidae	Polymastia		andrica	1
132046	<i>Polymastia</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Polymastiida	Polymastiidae	Polymastia			1
134215	<i>Quasillina brevis</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Polymastiida	Polymastiidae	Quasillina		brevis	2
134200	<i>Polymastia hemisphaerica</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Polymastiida	Polymastiidae	Radiella		hemisphaerica	5
170671	<i>Radiella</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Polymastiida	Polymastiidae	Radiella			1
134224	<i>Tentorium semisuberites</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Polymastiida	Polymastiidae	Tentorium		semisuberites	6
134232	<i>Weberella bursa</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Polymastiida	Polymastiidae	Weberella		bursa	1
131673	<i>Polymastiidae</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Polymastiida	Polymastiidae				7
134240	<i>Stylocordyla borealis</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Suberitida	Stylocordylidae	Stylocordyla		borealis	5
132063	<i>Stylocordyla</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Suberitida	Stylocordylidae	Stylocordyla			1
131777	<i>Homaxinella</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Suberitida	Suberitidae	Homaxinella			10
132071	<i>Rhizaxinella</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Suberitida	Suberitidae	Rhizaxinella			5
131994	<i>Stelletta</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Ancorinidae	Stelletta			1
131995	<i>Stryphnus</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Ancorinidae	Stryphnus			3
132005	<i>Geodia</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Geodiidae	Geodia			4
171330	<i>Craniella cranium</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Tetillidae	Craniella		cranium	2
132093	<i>Craniella</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Tetillidae	Craniella			8

134105	<i>Thenea levis</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Theneidae	Thenea		levis	3
134106	<i>Thenea muricata</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Theneidae	Thenea		muricata	9
132019	<i>Thenea</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Theneidae	Thenea			6
172017	<i>Asconema foliatum</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Hexactinellida	Lyssacinosida	Rossellidae	Asconema		foliatum	3
132122	<i>Asconema</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Hexactinellida	Lyssacinosida	Rossellidae	Asconema			2
132102	<i>Chonelasma</i>	Animalia	Porifera	Hexactinellida	Sceptrulophora	Euretidae	Chonelasma			3
558	<i>Porifera</i>	Animalia	Porifera							2
558	<i>Porifera</i>	Animalia	Porifera							10
558	<i>Porifera</i>	Animalia	Porifera							4
558	<i>Porifera</i>	Animalia	Porifera							7
558	<i>Porifera</i>	Animalia	Porifera							2
558	<i>Porifera</i>	Animalia	Porifera							4
558	<i>Porifera</i>	Animalia	Porifera							1
145541	<i>Ascophyllum nodosum</i>	Chromista	Ochrophyta	Phaeophyceae	Fucales	Fucaceae	Ascophyllum		nodosum	4
145548	<i>Fucus vesiculosus</i>	Chromista	Ochrophyta	Phaeophyceae	Fucales	Fucaceae	Fucus		vesiculosus	3
144129	<i>Fucus</i>	Chromista	Ochrophyta	Phaeophyceae	Fucales	Fucaceae	Fucus			3
852	<i>Rhodophyta</i>	Plantae	Rhodophyta							1
	<i>Benthos unidentified</i>									2
	<i>New Benthos Group 01</i>									1
	<i>New Species Alcyonacea 1</i>									1

	<i>New Species Bivalvia 1</i>									2
	<i>New Species Holothuroidea 1</i>									3
	<i>New Species Holothuroidea 2</i>									1
	<i>New Species Ophiuroidea 1</i>									1
	<i>New Species Polychaeta 1</i>									2
	<i>New Species Porifera 1</i>									8
	<i>New Species Porifera 2</i>									3
	<i>New Species Porifera 3</i>									2
	<i>New Species Porifera 4</i>									1
	<i>New Species Porifera 5</i>									1

4. Physical and Biological Oceanography

Team: Tobias Vonnahme, Mie Winding, Katharina Hammer, Pia Scaramiglia

4.1 Background and objectives

The overall aim of the pelagic sampling of this cruise was to characterize the oceanographic setting of the sampling sites which may be key drivers for the benthic ecosystem and carbon sequestration potential. The main objective was to identify different water masses, and to quantify biological biomass and productivity and their drivers. The transect from the coast towards the shelf is typically characterized by meltwater outflow from the fjords leading into the East Greenland current on the shelf, and the Irminger current feeding Atlantic water along the shelf break. In areas with deep troughs, such as along the selected sampling transects, Atlantic water may reach across the shelf affecting coastal processes.

Understanding the presence of Atlantic vs coastal water is important since Atlantic water is typically enriched in nutrients, which may lead to higher primary production and higher carbon sequestration potential. Pelagic primary production is a key source of carbon to the seafloor, where it can feed benthic ecosystems and may eventually be buried below the oxygenated layer, where it gets sequestered. Thus, primary production and chlorophyll a (Chl) biomass was measured, and the diversity and potential drivers (nutrients, light, stratification) were sampled. Due to the strong seasonality of pelagic production and biomass the data measured on this cruise will also be used for ground truthing of remote sensing products.

4.2 Sampling strategy and instrument description

Samples were taken in Southeast Greenland, where the Irminger current transporting Atlantic water along the shelf slope meets the cold and low salinity coastal water of the East Greenland current flowing along the shelf. Samples were taken along three transects from the coast, across the continental shelf, to the shelf break. All three transects followed troughs, which have the potential for deep water exchange (e.g. Atlantic water inflow across the shelf) and accumulation of sediments in the trough basin. 10, 7 and 6 samples for CTD and water sampling were taken along the three transects (Figure 4.1).

A CTD (Conductivity, Temperature, Depth) profile was taken using a Seabird SBE19Plus CTD profiler with additional sensors for fluorescence (proxy for Chlorophyll), oxygen, PAR, and turbidity. CTD profiles were taken at a speed of 30-60 m/min from the surface until 10 m over the bottom. A MARPORT system was used to measure the actual depth during the deployments to ensure that the CTD was at the desired depth. CTD profiles were taken from all stations. During the cruise, data for CTD profiles were uploaded from the CTD using the SEatermV2 software and processed using the SBEDataProcessing software. The data were further used for multibeam calibrations and analyses in R.

Water samples at 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 100, and 60m over the bottom were taken using a Niskin Rosette (Multiwater Sampler MWS12, Hydrobios Apparatebau, Kiel Germany) with 10 L Niskin bottles as described in the operation manual (ed 1/21). The trigger depths were preprogrammed (pressure triggered) using the Hydrobios OceanLab Software. CTD profiles and the Niskin bottle closing depths were recorded during the deployment and exported using the OceanLab Software. The Niskin rosette was also equipped with a MARPORT to ensure that the trigger depths were reached. Water samples were transferred into 5 and 10 L canisters or 50 mL Duran bottles and processed immediately as described below. Water samples were taken from all stations except OT1-4, due to time limitations.

Figure 4.1: Map of realised stations for CTD (blue) and Water (red) samples

4.3 Water processing

Water samples were processed for measurements of chlorophyll a (Chl, all depths), particulate organic carbon and nitrogen (60 m, bottom), bacteria cell counts (all depths at OT1; 1, 5, 20, 60, bottom, ChlMax at OT2 and OT3), phytoplankton communities (5 m, 20 m, Chl max), DNA (Chl max, Bottom), primary production and photophysiology (1-60 m), and Nutrients (all depths). The chlorophyll max was defined after fluorescence measurements on a PhytoPAM II (Walz).

The PhytoPAM II measures various photophysiological parameters and estimates primary production as electron transport rates based on the variable fluorescence of chlorophyll under dark and light conditions using the PhytoWin3 (Walz) Software. The Phytopam II can also differentiate photophysiological parameters of different algae groups (blue algae, green algae, brown algae, cyanobacteria). The gain of the instrument was set automatically (most samples between 22 and 23) and blanked using a filtered sample (0.45 μm syringe filter).

The yield of photosystem II indicates the stress level of the phytoplankton and was measured on dark adapted (at least 15 min) samples. Chlorophyll was then measured for the 4 algae groups, but the values are biased to specific reference cultures and additional Chl measurements of extracted samples are still necessary (see below). Primary production was estimated as electron transport rates under various light intensities. Samples from 5 m, 20 m, and the Chl Max were measured in triplicates, while all other samples with sufficient Chl concentrations were measured once. All measurements were done in the cold room at 7°C.

For chlorophyll measurements, 500 or 300 ml water was filtered onto 25 mm GF/F filter using a vacuum pump (max 0.3mbar underpressure) in the dark. The filters were folded and transferred into 11 mL plastic vials before adding 5 mL 98% ethanol and storage at -20°C until measurements on a fluorometer at the GINR in Nuuk.

For POC/PON samples, 5L water was filtered onto 47 mm pre-combusted (450°C) and pre-weighed GF/F filters before storage in petri dishes at -20°C.

Nutrient samples were prefiltered into 11 mL plastic vials using a 0.45 µm syringe filter and stored at -20°C. For each depth two samples were prepared, one for external measurements of nitrate, nitrite, silicate, phosphate, and ammonium on a nutrient analyser. The other sample will be used for nitrate and nitrite measurements using colorimetric methods at the GINR. The samples measured at the GINR will allow early data access for a master thesis, while the samples measured on the nutrient analyser provide a broader spectrum of different nutrients.

For bacteria cell counts, 1.8 mL water was transferred into cryovials before adding 40 µL 25% Glutaraldehyde and storage at -80°C. The samples will be analysed using a flow cytometer.

Water samples for phytoplankton communities were taken in 100 mL brown borosilicate glass bottles and fixed with 1-2% neutral Lugol solution. The samples will be counted under a light microscope and identified at the GINR.

DNA samples were taken by filtering 2-5 L water onto 0.22 µm Sterivex filters using a peristaltic pump. The filter will later be used for metabarcoding analyses of 16S rRNA (bacteria and archaea) and 18S rRNA (protists) marker genes.

4.4 Preliminary findings

While most samples will be analysed after the cruise, data from the CTD profiler are already available and allow a first insight into the oceanographic setting of the sampling sites. While the transects show some differences in the extent of Atlantic and coastal water masses, the overall structure is comparable and the transect of OT1 is shown below (Figure 4.2).

Atlantic water masses of the Irminger current are characterized by high temperature and salinity, and low oxygen concentrations, while coastal water masses of the East Greenland current are characterized by low temperature and salinity, and high oxygen concentrations.

In all transects the AW was abundant at the shelf break, and coastal water close to the coast. However, AW intrusions into the trough were observed at all three transects. While the transects followed the troughs, there is no clear gradient of AW from the shelf break towards the coast, instead patches of AW appear in single stations on the shelf. This indicates that the AW can enter the trough along a different route, but it also shows that AW can cross the shelf and potentially reach the fjords introducing heat and nutrients onto the shelf, which will affect primary production and plankton communities.

Fig 4.2: Cross transect of A) Oxygen (O_2), B) Salinity (S), and C) Temperature ($T^{\circ}\text{C}$) along transect OT1 (D).

The added fluorescence sensor on the CTD can give a first impression of Chlorophyll concentrations across the transects. At all transects the highest fluorescence is found along the shelf slope, which may be due to the typically higher nitrate concentrations in Atlantic water, but which may also be associated to shelf break upwelling, or advection of old blooms with the Irminger current. To some degree, a second fluorescence maxima can be found close to the coast, which may be fuelled by coastal processes such as coastal or subglacial upwelling. Some of the fluorescence maxima at the shelf slope are below 30 m, which is below the depth that satellites can detect, indicating some upcoming challenges in using remote sensing data to estimate the annual productivity of the study area.

Fig 4.2. Fluorescence profiles (proxy for Chl) along the three transects from the shelf slope (0km) to the coast. A) OT1, B) OT2, C) OT3.

5. Sediment biogeochemistry

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5.1 Background and objectives

Short core samples (1m) were collected to investigate sediment geochemistry, biogeochemistry and ecology in the SE Greenland continental shelf. These cores were preserved to allow laboratory determination of variability in seafloor organic material, organic carbon, inorganic carbon, nutrients, and biota along three different transects (Table 5.1). The cores were sliced at specified intervals to facilitate comparison with wider polar data (e.g. those taken by Changing Arctic Oceans cruises in the Barents Sea and ICEBERGS along the West Antarctic Peninsula (Sands et al., 2018; Zwerschke et al., 2022)). One core was taken for respiration measurements on board.

5.2 Sampling strategy and instrument description

The sampling strategy and sites for the Deep Trace scientific cruise of RV Tarajoq were planned along three transects across the SE Greenland continental shelf (Figure 1). These transects spanned from coast to the continental slope just beyond the shelf break and were designed to incorporate some areas likely to be formed of soft sediment types. Approximately eight days of sampling time was organised such that attempts at sediment capture would predominantly occur during the night and alternate with other apparatus deployments, such as beam trawl and video-sledge.

All sediment cores were collected using a multi-corer at the approximate location of predetermined sites (Figure 5.1). In each case a decision whether, and exactly where, to deploy was based on prior consideration of both multibeam and sub-bottom profiling data (and sometimes time and weather constraints).

The instrument used to capture sediment was a KC Denmark Multicorer 70,000 (model) fitted with six Perspex core sleeves (800mm length, 105mm diameter). This is an ideal instrument to sample the upper 50 cm of sediment, overlying bottom water and usually intact sediment-water interface. Before deployment, core sleeves were loaded into the instrument and the spring closing mechanism was locked open using pins. The instrument was lifted slightly on the deck to remove the two safety bars (which prevent it triggering when away from the seabed). It was then manoeuvred over the side of the vessel and lowered to the seabed using a side gantry winch. As the six round feet of the multicorer frame land on the seabed, the middle section containing the six core tubes penetrates into the sediment, pressed down by the onboard weights. The corer was left to settle on the seabed for 1-2 minutes and then pulled up slowly, triggering the release pins and allowing the trap doors to snap shut, sealing the sleeves and retaining any captured sediment within the tubes.

The protocol for using the multicorer was adapted throughout the cruise. Initially 120 kg of weights were fitted, which was increased to 240 kg and eventually 360 kg. Initial descent speed was 60m per minute, decreasing to 20m per minute on approach to the seabed (approximately 50m above), and then slowing to 5m per minute in the final stages. However, due to concerns regarding the instrument being lifted off the seabed through pitch, roll and drift of the ship the 5 m descent portion was removed and a final descent of 20 m per minute continued until the deployed wire length was at least 20 m greater than the depth of seabed. The bottom time duration was increased in later deployments from 1-2 minutes to 4-5 minutes. Initial lifting speed was 20 m per minute later increasing to 30 m per minute. The winch auto-spooler required truing on a couple of occasions and occasionally the winch wire slipped in spooling and the winch had to be stopped and reversed to achieve smooth spooling. The path of the multicorer to and from the hydrography hanger to outboard requires tight navigation around the deck railing, not all of which can temporarily fold away (Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.1: Realised multicore stations

Figure 5.2 Deployment of multicorer through the side gantry on RV Tarajiq and successful recovery of multicorer

5.3 Specific core fate

The multicorer was deployed 29 times (Figure 5.2), of which cores of sediment were successfully retrieved on 13 occasions. During the failed deployments the multicorer either closed by contact with the water (only during transect OT1, which was fixed by replacing the trigger pins with longer pins), or hit hard bottom (bedrock or gravel). For each successful recovery the aim was to use all six cores. Three of the cores were sampled for organic matter, organic carbon and inorganic carbon, of which one was also used to investigate eDNA. One core was used for total and diffusive (bacterial) oxygen consumption and to determine the oxygen penetration depth, One core was taken for total organic matter, Chlorophyll a (Proxy for lability), Porosity, and bacteria cell counts. The remaining core was used for porewater extraction for nutrient measurements and subsequently sieved for biota. The details of these are given in the following three sections.

Table 5.1 Table of all multicore deployments and associated sample capture

Tarajoq Station number	Planned Station ID	Carbon samples Label ID	Biogeo Samples Label ID	Date	Time (UTC)	Latitude	Longitude	Ship depth	Marport depth	Carbon rep 1	Carbon rep 2	Carbon rep 3	Epifauna	Biogeochemistry 1	Biogeochemistry 2	eDNA	Total cores
1	OT1.8			19/09/2024	22:41	64.02.962	36.39.416	366	3,707	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	OT1.8			19/09/2024	23:40	64.02.756	36.39.973	360	369	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	OT1.6	S01	B01	20/09/2024	04:50	64.18.274	37.34.669	714	726	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	5
12	OT1.4			20/09/2024	19:00	64.46.218	38.16.412	665	684	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	OT1.4			20/09/2024	21:54	64.45.734	38.13.499	621	630	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	OT1.2		B02	21/09/2024	03:58	65.15.406	38.20.009	492	487	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
17	OT1.2	S02	B03	21/09/2024	05:31	65.15.580	38.20.040	530	539	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
20	OT1.1		B04	21/09/2024	09:21	65.29.190	38.17.597	360	369	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
21	OT1.1			21/09/2024	10:30	65.29.432	38.16.768	420	430	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	OT1.3			21/09/2024	22:06	64.58.708	38.19.255	785	798	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	OT1.3			21/09/2024	23:21	64.58.664	38.19.824	781	795	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
32	OT1.5	S03	B05	22/09/2024	05:45	64.36.802	38.05.059	678	689	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	5
42	OT1.9			23/09/2024	00:36	63.55.492	36.12.058	1,399	1,412	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48	-			23/09/2024	18:00	aborted	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
50	OT2.6	S04	B06	23/09/2024	20:49	63.31.688	39.43.428	620	631	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
51	OT2.5	S05	B07	23/09/2024	23:37	63.39.143	39.59.651	849	833	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
53	OT2.4		B08	24/09/2024	04:32	63.44.750	40.06.499	848	868	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2
66	OT2.1			24/09/2024	22:26	64.10.090	40.19.425	759	777	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
67	OT2.1			24/09/2024	23:45	64.09.898	40.20.047	761	778	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
68	OT2.2			25/09/2024	02:30	63.59.987	40.14.935	1,038	1,064	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
69	OT2.3			25/09/2024	05:30	aborted	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
81	OT2.8	S06	B09	26/09/2024	00:13	63.11.91	39.45.63	1,329	1,363	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	6
96	OT3.3			26/09/2024	21:01	62.25.153	41.15.219	543	553	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
99	OT3.1	S07	B10	27/09/2024	03:28	62.34.926	42.02.842	266	277	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
106	OT3.X	S08	B11	27/09/2024	11:48	62.27.720	41.29.577	750	740	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
107	OT3.3			27/09/2024	13:47	62.25.884	41.20.968	628	642	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
108	OT3.4	S09	B12	27/09/2024	17:30	62.19.219	40.53.540	661	676	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	7
110	OT3.5		B13	27/09/2024	21:08	62.14.806	40.35.142	416	423	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
111	OT3.6			27/09/2024	23:43	62.11.349	40.24.429	1,409	1,418	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 5.2: Specific fate of biogeochemistry cores

Tarajoq Station number	Planned Station ID	Biogeo Labels ID	Biogeo slicing	Porewater	TOU	DOU	Oxygenated layer [cm]
4	OT1.6	B01	X		X		2.7
16,17	OT1.2	B02,B03	X	X	X		
20	OT1.1	B04	X		X		
32	OT1.5	B05	X	X	X	X	4.5
50	OT2.6	B06	X	X	X	X	3.6
51	OT2.5	B07	X	X	X	X	2.4
53	OT2.4	B08	X		X	X	NA
81	OT2.8	B09	X	X	X	X	NA
99	OT3.1	B10	X	X	X	X	1.7
106	OT3.X	B11	X	X	X	X	NA
108	OT3.4	B12	X	X	X	X	3.4
110	OT3.5	B13	X		X	X	5

5.4 Organic and carbon content

Team: David Barnes, Ryan Mathews, Duncan Sinclair, Narissa Bax

On nine occasions the corer returned six sediment cores. Three replicate cores were each sliced at intervals of 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22, 24, 26, 28 and 30 cm horizons. On one occasion additional slices were made at 40, 50 and 60 cm horizons for three replicate cores. These core slices were then snap frozen at -80°C for 12 hours and then transferred for storage in the -20°C freezer. These will be processed at GINR, Nuuk, to investigate organic matter, organic carbon and inorganic carbon spatiotemporal variability. The horizon slice regime was planned to compare with similar multiyear data from Arctic Barents Sea and West Antarctica.

5.5 eDNA

Team: Narissa Bax

For the nine successful sampling occasions eDNA was sampled at three core sections—the surface, 5 cm, and 11 cm— for one replicate. For every sample, 2 ml of sediment was conserved in 2 ml of RNAlater. These samples will be sent for analysis by colleagues at Aarhus University in Denmark and Firum on the Faroe Islands to answer the following questions:

- Is macroalgal detritus present in the sediments in East Greenland shelf, slope, and trough areas?
- Which macroalgal species are present?

Estimates of the absolute (qPCR) and relative (NGS) abundances of certain algae may also be investigated.

This work is a component of the GINR BlueCea project, which seeks to track macroalgal production to possible blue carbon sinks and assess blue carbon potential across the Greenland-Iceland-Faroe-Scotland Ridge (The Ridge). This work utilises eDNA to detect macroalgae in seafloor sediments to estimate macroalgal contributions to carbon content, and determine the presence or absence of different algae in the sediment to better understand biodiversity with more accuracy than other techniques.

5.6 Biogeochemistry

Team: Tobias Vonnahme, Pia Scaramiglia

For Oxygen microsensor profiling, three subcores of one core were taken using 50 mL cut-off syringe. Compression of the sediment was avoided by keeping the syringe cap levelled with the water surface. The subcores were profiled for oxygen profiles using a UniSense Oxygen microsensor with a 100 μm tip (Figure 5.6.1, Table 5.2). The microsensor was calibrated using air saturated water and a 0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ standard solution. The oxygen profile was taken using an automated microprofiler and the SensorTraceSuite v3.4 Software by UniSense. The profiles started about 0.5 cm over the sediment surface and profiled in 100 μm steps with a waiting time of 3s and a measurement time of 1s. In case of sediment cores containing rocks or shells only the diffusive boundary layer (dbl) was measured (a few 100 μm into the sediment), while the remaining cores were profiled until the oxygen penetration depth (0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ oxygen) was reached. When possible, full profiles were taken once at all cores, while dbl measurements were taken three times per core. The dbl will allow to calculate diffusive oxygen uptake at the sediment surface, which translates to bacterial respiration. Conversion factors then allow to estimate carbon remineralisation rates. The oxygen penetration depth was determined to identify the depth at which carbon is remineralised aerobically, which is the most efficient carbon remineralisation process. Organic carbon below the oxygenated layer is considered sequestered.

Figure 5.6.1: Example of an oxygen microsensor profile showing the diffusive boundary layer (dbl) and oxygenated layer.

Total respiration was measured on surface sediment (0-1 cm) using oxygen measurements of a sediment slurry in 4 mL Firesting (PyroScience) oxygen vials. Ca 0.5 mL (exact weight was determined each time) was transferred into the vials and filled up with sterile filtered (0.2 μm Sterivex filter) seawater from the same core. Oxygen depletion was then measured using the Firesting system and the OxygenLogger Software (PyroScience) (Figure 5.6.2A). Three vials were incubated with the sediment slurry, while one vial was incubated with sterile filtered seawater as blank. The measurements were continuously temperature corrected. All vials were calibrated using air saturated water and a 0 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ standard solution. Incubations ran for at least 5 hours. The total oxygen uptake represents total respiration by bacteria and infauna and can be converted to aerobic carbon remineralisation.

For the total organic matter, Chlorophyll a (Proxy for lability), Porosity, flow cytometry and DNA, we were using one single core and slice it at different depth (0-1cm, 1-2cm, 2-5cm, 5-10cm, 10-15cm).

The biogeochemical core was sliced in layers of 0-1, 1-2, 2-5, 5-10, and 10-15 cm. The slices exceeding 1 cm were homogenized before subsampling (After porosity sampling). Important notes for depth from 2-5cm, 5-10cm, 10-15cm: To make sure the data was making sense, we had to take a piece of the whole layer and mix it together before taking any samples

otherwise the depth could only be from 2-3cm if you use a spatula straight on the slice for example.

The porosity was sampled using a cut off 10 mL syringe to obtain the volume of each sample in ml. Once sampled, the “wet” material was weighed wet and put to dry in an oven at 70°C. The dehydration process can take 2 to 3 days. Once dried, the samples are weighed again and stored in a box for potential later use. The volume to wet weight to dry weight ratios allow calculating porosity, which is important for comparisons of the other parameters with other studies and for DOU calculations from the microsensors profiles.

One of the challenges of this stage is that on the first two layers, the material is often not very dense and sometimes too liquid to be drawn into the syringe properly. When this was the case we would leave a 2-ml gap on the syringe, fill it by pressing it against one of the metal plates used for cutting, and slide a spatula underneath to collect a volume without compressing the material.

DNA samples were collected on the top slice only and were then stored in the freezer at -80°C. The samples will be used for metabarcoding of the 16S rRNA for studying the bacterial diversity and their metabolic potential.

Chlorophyll a was collected on each slice in 11 mL plastic tubes, afterwards the samples were weighed, and some Ethanol (5 ml of 98% ethanol) was added in the tubes and stored in the -20°C freezer. Chlorophyll a will be measured at GINR and will give a proxy for the lability of the organic matter in the sediment.

Samples for bacteria cell counts (FC, flow cytometry) were collected on each slice in yellow cryo vials and weighed, afterwards sterile filtered (0.22 µm Sterivex filter) sea water from the core was added up to the lead and one dose (40µm) of chemical (25% Gluraldehyde) was added after that. The tubes were then stored in the -80°C freezer.

For nutrients measurements we were using a modified core sleeve with holes at every 2 cm from the bottom to the top. We were covering the holes with tape and then use it as a normal core. In the future, we suggest having two of the “special core sleeves”.

For nutrient analysis, we collected bottom water with a syringe from the top of the sediment. The water was sterile filtered (0.22 µm Sterivex filter) before being stored in nutrient vials. To be able to filter the water inside the core at different depth, we opened the pre-drilled holes of the first five depths through the tape, starting from the first hole covered by sediment. We inserted rhizone filters and added syringes at the end of each one to collect the water using a cryovial to keep the syringe open (5mL) and create a vacuum. Once the syringes had been rinsed, we filled each nutrient tube (Figure 5.6.2). We also measured the size of the core and the depth of the holes for each one. Once porewater collection was accomplished, infauna of the core was sampled.

Figure 5.6.2: Set-up for A) micro profiling and B) porewater collection

5.7 Infauna

Team: David Barnes, Ryan Mathews, Laure de Montety, Alenya Merz

Cores available for infauna estimation were gently washed over a 1 mm sieve to remove all sand and mud. Pebbles were removed by hand. Small delicate infauna such as worms were picked out of the sample and stored in ethanol. The remaining sample was stored in a ziplock bag and frozen at -20°C . This was not always possible, owing to time constraints. In this case the whole sample was frozen at -20°C for later sorting and identification. Preserving all samples in ethanol was unfortunately not possible, owing to a lack of ethanol on board.

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